

Effect of Peer-Mediated Intervention and Social Skill Training on Social Competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

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Abstract

The study determined the impact of peer-mediated intervention and social skill intervention on the social competence of children with social communication disorder. Additionally, it examined how social anxiety and gender moderate the social competence of the participant. A quasi-experimental design with a 2x2x2 factorial matrix was used. The participants were chosen via a purposive sampling technique and randomized to experimental groups 1 (PMI), 2 (SST), and a control group, with 15 participants each. Treatment lasted for ten weeks and was guided by 5 hypotheses. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Sidak Post-hoc test at a 0.05 level of significance were used to analyse the data. The study's findings demonstrated a significant primary effect of interventions on children with social communication disorder's social competence ($F(1, 44) = 143.147; p < 0.05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .8$). Social skill training produced the highest adjusted post-social competency mean score, while peer-mediated intervention had the lowest mean score (51.78). Additionally, the findings demonstrated that social anxiety and gender significantly impact the social competence of children with social communication disorder ($\eta^2 = 0.13$). The study concluded that children with social communication disorder benefit more from social skill training in terms of their social competence. The result indicated that speech-language pathologists should employ social skill training to improve the social competence of children with social communication disorders.

Keywords: Peer-Mediated Intervention; Social Skill Training; Social Competence; Social Communication Disorder

Introduction

Communication is an essential aspect of human and animal life, serving as a vehicle for sharing information, establishing interpersonal relationships, and transmitting culture and societal norms across generations. For children, communication forms the foundation upon which they learn language, social expectations, and behavioural norms vital for social interaction. However, successful communication extends beyond spoken words. It includes the ability to interpret context, understand

social cues, and apply prior knowledge to derive meaning, which is commonly referred to as social communication. Social communication involves using language appropriately in social contexts. It encompasses interpreting both verbal and non-verbal cues, understanding the speaker's intent, and adapting communication based on context and societal norms. Some children, however, face challenges in these areas. These difficulties often manifest as an inability to follow group conversations, misinterpretation of social cues, or inappropriate social behaviour, all of which can undermine social competence.

Social competence is the ability to participate in effective and appropriate social interactions. It includes a wide spectrum of social, emotional, and cognitive abilities necessary for successful social adaptation and the maintenance of interpersonal relationships. Social competence develops gradually, beginning in early childhood through interaction with caregivers, peers, and the surrounding environment. As children grow, play and social engagement provide critical opportunities for learning and internalising social norms and behaviours. A disruption in this developmental process, particularly in social communication, can have long-term negative impacts such as social disengagement, behavioural problems, and rejection by peers (APA, 2013). According to the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association. (n.d.) language use in social situations is termed social communication, and it includes pragmatics, language processing, social interaction, and social cognition. Deficit in these core areas has been identified as social communication disorder (henceforth SCD).

Children with social communication disorder (SCD) sometimes have challenges with verbal/ nonverbal communication in social situations. American Speech-Language-Hearing Association. (n.d.) states that social cognition, pragmatics, language processing, and social interaction are all impaired in SCD. Even though children with SCD may have age-appropriate vocabulary and syntax, their impaired use of language in social settings often leads to misunderstandings and inappropriate social responses. These challenges make targeted intervention essential.

Two intervention strategies that have shown promise in addressing social communication deficits are Peer-Mediated Intervention (PMI) and Social Skills Training (SST). PMI involves training peers who are ordinarily developing to interact with children with SCD in structured ways, fostering naturalistic opportunities for communication and social engagement. Research has shown that PMI can greatly increase the number and quality of peer relationships for children with communication disorders (Zhang and Wheeler, 2011; Whalon, Conroy, Martinez, and Werch, 2015). Social skill training, on the other hand, is a structured therapeutic approach based on behavioural and social learning theories that seeks to teach children different social skills, including starting a conversation, reading social signs, and meticulously handling peer disagreement. Studies (Gresham & Elliott, 2001; Cappadocia & Weiss, 2011)

have demonstrated that SST can help children with a range of communication and developmental difficulties become more socially competent.

In addition to intervention type, two other factors, social anxiety and gender, may influence social competence outcomes. Social anxiety, attributes by extreme fear of social scrutiny, often overlaps with social communication deficits, contributing to avoidance behaviours and limiting opportunities for social learning. Gender may also play a role, though existing research presents mixed findings regarding its influence on the prevalence and manifestation of SCD (Reinhardt, Wetherby, Schatschneider & Lord, 2015; Braza, Azurmendi, Muñoz, Carreras, Braza, García, & Sánchez-Martín, 2009). These inconsistencies highlight the need for further investigation into how gender and social anxiety interact with intervention strategies.

Although numerous studies have examined interventions for social communication and competence, there is limited empirical evidence on the combined use of PMI and SST, particularly within the cultural and educational context of Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. There is a need to explore the effectiveness of these interventions among children with SCD in this locality, taking into account the moderating effects of gender and social anxiety. Thus, the study examined how social skills training and peer-mediated intervention enhance the social competence of children with SCD in Ibadan Metropolis, with a particular focus on how gender and social anxiety interact. It is anticipated that the results will offer significant perspectives to educators, therapists, and legislators who aim to improve the social functioning and general development of children with SCD.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant main effect of treatments (Peer Mediated Intervention and Social skill training) on social competence of children with social communication disorder (participants).

H0₂: There is no significant main effect of gender on social competence of the participants.

H0₃: There is no significant main effect of social anxiety disorder on social competence of the participants.

H0₄: There is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on social competence of the participants.

H0₅: There is no significant interaction effects of treatments and social anxiety disorder on social competence of the participants.

Methodology

This study used a quasi-experimental approach with a 3×2×2 factorial matrix. The population of the study comprised all the children with social communication disorder in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. 45 (23 males and 22 females) children selected via a multi-stage sampling technique took part in the study. They were assigned to three groups randomly: group 1 (PMI), group 2 (SST), and group 3, the control group, all with 15 participants each.

Three major research tools used include the Social Competence Rating Scale, by Brian Spitzberg, with the assistance of Thomas Adams. The Social Communication Disorder Scale was developed by Kenneth Ghiple and Julie McAfee in the year 2016, and the Social Anxiety Scale was developed by Michael Liebowitz (2003). The Social Communication Disorder Scale was used to ascertain the diagnosis of social communication disorder. The Social Competence Rating Scale was employed to measure the data gathered before and after the treatment. Social anxiety scale was adopted to measure the social anxiety of the participants. The treatment lasted for ten weeks. The participants were exposed to treatments (PMI and SST) and a conventional programme. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Sidak Post Hoc analysis were used to analysed data.

Result

H0₁: There is no significant main effect of treatments (Peer-Mediated Intervention and Social skill training) on social competence of children with social communication disorder.

Table A: Post-Social competence by Treatment, Gender, and Social anxiety using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2561.098	12	213.425	143.172	.000	.982
Intercept	52.508	1	52.508	35.224	.000	.524
Pre-Test	1405.665	1	1405.665	942.965	.000	.967
Treatment	426.74	2	213.387	143.147	.000*	.8
Social Anxiety	2.004	1	2.004	1.344	.255	.040
Gender	.037	1	.037	.025	.876	.001
Treatment* Social Anxiety	6.044	2	3.022	2.027	.148	.112
Treatment* Gender	.100	2	.050	.034	.967	.002
Social Anxiety* Gender	7.364	1	7.364	4.940	.033*	.134
Treatment* Social Anxiety* Gender	11.360	2	5.680	3.810	.033*	.192
Error	47.702	32	1.491			
Total	145752.000	45				
Corrected Total	2608.800	44				

R Squared = 0.98 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.98)

*denotes significant p<0.05

The social competence of children with social communication difficulties was significantly impacted by treatments (social skill training and peer-mediated intervention) ($F(1, 44) = 143.147$; $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .8$), according to Table 1. 8% is the effect size. This indicates that children with social communication disorders differ significantly in their pre and post social competence. The estimated marginal mean of the intervention groups was calculated to ascertain the extent of influence across treatment groups; the results are displayed in Table B.

Table B: Estimated Marginal Means of the treatment groups (Post-Social Competence) and Control group

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Peer-Mediated Intervention (PmI)	55.69	0.36	54.95	56.42
Social-Skill Training (SST)	61.74	0.43	60.85	62.62
Control (C)	51.78	0.40	50.97	52.60

Table B showed that the adjusted mean score for post-social competence was highest among children with social communication disorder in the Social-Skill Training (SST) treatment group 2 ($\chi = 61.74$), followed by those in the Peer-Mediated Intervention (PmI) treatment group 1 ($\chi = 55.69$) and those in the conventional group ($\chi = 51.78$). Table C displays the results of the Sidak post-hoc test, which was administered to all treatment groups to determine which one had a marked impact on the social competence of the participants.

Table C: Sidak Post-hoc Analysis of Post-Social Competence by Treatment and Control Group

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error
Peer-Mediated Intervention (PmI)	Social-Skill Training Grp	-6.051*	.576
	Control Group	3.903*	.537
Social-Skill Training (SST)	Peer-Mediated Intervention	6.051*	.576
	Control Group	9.955*	.589
Control (C)	Peer-Mediated Intervention	-3.903*	.537
	Social Skill Training Grp	-9.955*	.589

* denotes significant $p < 0.05$

The table above shows that children with social communication disorder who received social skill training had significantly higher post-social competence than those who received peer-mediated intervention and control. Additional findings show that children with social communication disorder who received peer-mediated intervention had significantly different post-social competency mean scores than their control group counterparts. This suggests that, in terms of the SC of children with social communication disorder, the ANCOVA result's notable difference is caused by the differences between the treatment groups (peer-mediated intervention and social-skill training) and the control group.

H0₂: There is no significant main effect of social anxiety on social competence of children with social communication disorder

Social anxiety did not significantly impact the participants (children with social communication disorder) in the focused area social competence, according to Table A ($F(1, 44) = 1.34$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.04$). This implies that social anxiety has no effect on the social competence of the participants

H0₃: There is no significant main effect of gender on the social competence of children with social communication disorder

This study showed that gender did not significantly affect the SC of children with social communication disorder, according to Table A ($F(1, 44) = 0.25$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.001$). This means that gender has no effect on the social competence of the participants.

H0₄: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and social anxiety on the social competence of children with social communication disorder

The result of the study showed that there is a marked impact of intervention and social anxiety on the social competence of children with social communication disorder ($F(2, 43) = 2.027$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .112$). This implies that the social competence of the participants is impacted by treatment and social anxiety.

H0₅: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on the social competence of children with social communication disorder

This study revealed that the SC of children with SCD was not significantly impacted by treatment or gender ($F(2, 43) = 0.34$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.002$). This means that intervention and gender had no impact on the SC of children with SCD.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

Peer-Mediated Intervention and Social Skill Strategies on Social Competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

The results analysis showed a substantial primary effect of treatment on the social competence of children with SCD, but SST was more effective than the PMI. Studies have affirmed that SST is effective in improving the social skills (Wang and Spillane, 2009; Karaoğlu, 2011; Pekdoğan, 2016; Gökel & Dağlı, 2017; Larose, Ouellet-Morin, Vergunst, Vitaro & Girard, 2020). This is because social skills training focuses on a variety of distinct social behaviour (such as making eye contact, salutations, relevant actions, showing appreciation), language aspects (of words spoken, intonation), and interactional skills, as opposed to peer-mediated interventions, which, if poorly managed, may not expose participants to target skills as intended. Additionally, the control group's members receive no formal therapy.

However, PMI is a successful treatment method for enhancing the SC of children with SCD. Young children with social communication disorder have been found to benefit from the PMI as an intervention for their social competency needs (Martinez, Waters, Conroy, and Reichow, 2019; Dueñas, Plavnick & Goldstein, 2020). Moreover, PMI is regarded as an evidence-based approach with distinct benefits over other social competence interventions (Odom, Cox, & Brock, 2013).

Social Anxiety on Social Competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

The results indicate that social anxiety did not significantly affect the SC of children with social communication disorder. However, several studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between social deficiencies and poor social communication abilities. The link between social anxiety and social competence issues has also been validated by cross-sectional studies. According to the results, social anxiety did not significantly affect the SC of children with social communication disorder; however, several studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between social deficits and poor social communication skills, and cross-sectional studies have also confirmed the link between social competence issues and SA. For instance, research using parent-report questionnaires has revealed that children with SA disorder have more social competence issues than children with other anxiety disorders (Lau, Zhou, Yuan, Parigoris, Rosenberg, and Weisz, 2023), this suggests a specific relationship between social competence and Social Anxiety (Halldorsson, Castelijjn, and Creswell, 2019). The findings revealed that difficulties in social competence may underlie the development of SA (Rapee, and Spence, 2004) and not vice versa. This simply implies that the impact of treatments (peer-mediated intervention and social skill training) on social anxiety does not necessarily reduce social incompetence, since social anxiety does not increase social competence, but difficulties in social competence may increase social anxiety.

Gender on Social Competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

The findings revealed no interaction impact between gender and treatments on the social competence of children with disorder in social communication. However, various studies reported gender differences (Chaplin, and Aldao, 2013). Accordingly, Daniel Hajovskya, Jacqueline, Caemmererb, Benjamin, and Masonc (2021) found that low social skills are more common in guys than in girls. Furthermore, according to the gender intensification theory, gender may be associated with a perception of the value of social skills.

The theory explained gender differences by suggesting that girls place a higher value on interpersonal relationships than boys do, and that because their peers and family have socialized them, they are more self-conscious and conforming about their behaviour in school, which leads to improved academic performance (Korlat, Foerst, Schultes, Schober, Spiel, and Kollmayer, 2021).

Treatments and Social Anxiety on Social Competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

The findings demonstrated that the interaction of therapies and social anxiety did not significantly impact the social competence of children with social communication disorder. Nonetheless, several reviews of research found a link between social anxiety and social competence problems. According to research children with social anxiety disorder have more social competence issues compared to children with other anxiety disorders (Halldorsson, Castelijm, Creswell, 2019; Pickard, Rijsdijk, Happé, and Mandy, 2017; Lau, Zhou, Yuan, Parigoris, Rosenberg, and Weisz, 2023; Asgarabad, Steinsbekk, and Wichstrøm, 2023), suggesting that social competence difficulties may not be universal in children with social anxiety (Kaeppler & Erath, 2017; Pickard, Rijsdijk, Happé & Mandy, 2017; and Stark, Groves & Kofler, 2023).

Treatments and Gender on Social competence of Children with Social Communication Disorder

The findings showed that the participants' social competency was not significantly impacted by the interaction of the treatment and gender. However, compared to their male counterparts who received the same treatment, the female children with social communication disorder who received social skill training performed and improved better. However, the results of the peer-mediated intervention showed that male participants outperformed female participants who received the same intervention. In line with this study, Anme, Shinohara, Sugisawa, and Tong (2010) used the IRS score to demonstrate how gender differs in parenting and children's social abilities. The outcome demonstrated how boys and girls behave differently. Additionally, a study by Larose, Ouellet-Morin, and Vergunst, (2020) examined the impact of a social skills programme on social behaviours of children at daycare facilities in low-socioeconomic-status neighbourhoods. The findings revealed that the programme's effects were moderated by the gender of the child. It also revealed a decrease in the degree of disruptive behaviours in girls, but not in boys.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are thus proposed:

Introduction of Evidence-Based Interventions into Educational Practice

Educational authorities and school administrators in Ibadan Metropolis should incorporate Peer-Mediated Intervention (PMI) and Social Skills Training (SST) into the curriculum of inclusive and special education settings. These interventions have been shown to enhance the competence of children with Social Communication Disorder (SCD) in social skills.

Training and Capacity Building for Teachers

Teachers, especially those working in inclusive classrooms, should undergo regular professional development on strategies for implementing PMI and SST. Such training will equip them with practical tools for facilitating peer interactions and structured social learning.

Early Identification and Intervention

School psychologists, speech-language pathologists, and educators should work collaboratively to identify children with SCD at an early stage. Timely intervention is critical, as it improves long-term outcomes and mitigates the risk of social withdrawal, anxiety, and peer rejection.

Peer Sensitization and Inclusion

Creating an inclusive school culture where typically developing peers are taught empathy, patience, and communication strategies can enhance the effectiveness of PMI. Structured programs should be introduced to train peer tutors or mentors who can support children with SCD during classroom and play activities.

Addressing Social Anxiety and Gender Dynamics

Given the moderating effects of social anxiety and gender, intervention strategies should be tailored to accommodate individual differences. Children exhibiting social withdrawal or anxiety symptoms should receive integrated psychosocial support, and further studies should explore how gender-specific approaches might enhance outcomes.

Conclusion

The study revealed the importance of early therapeutic intervention, which cannot be over-emphasised with great reference to peer-mediated intervention and social skill training for the management of social competence of children with social communication disorder. More importantly, the psychological, physical, and cognitive impacts that adversely affect the social relationship and competence of children with social communication disorder, thereby making them live below their potential. Therefore, speech and language therapists and other experts must be involved in the rehabilitation of children with SCD and adopt these treatments for the management of children with social communication disorder. In addition, social skill training has been established to be more effective than peer-mediated intervention; this factor should therefore be noted when choosing the treatment options.

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